

VALKYRIES

D7.2 Datasets Management and Benchmarking

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.2 – Datasets Management and Benchmarking begins by addressing the fundamentals of datasets, including data cleansing and transformation, and considering the challenges presented by unbalanced data. At the same time, it highlights the importance of data visualization as an essential tool in any data analysis, facilitating both the understanding and effective communication of results.

After that, the document presents a study of the state of the art of datasets related to emergency situations, allowing to know and study the existing datasets in the literature in order to create our specific one for the VALKYRIES project.

Next, the report presents the dataset created for the VALKYRIES project, where an in-depth analysis is made indicating the data that integrate the dataset and the steps taken to improve the data quality. Moreover, models with better results allow the generation of quality models that give more optimal results, leading to more accurate predictions.

Finally, the deliverable addresses tailored ethical and regulatory issues of managing and disclosing sensitive data. Privacy and data security are paramount, especially when dealing with sensitive data related to emergency response operations.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

Today's world is increasingly immersed in the digital age, with data being generated at a dizzying pace from multiple sources. Among the most critical data are those related to emergency response operations, which can be vital to saving lives and maintaining stability in our societies.

In this context of increasing digitalisation and the need for accurate data, artificial intelligence, in particular machine learning, has emerged as a powerful field that can help extract valuable patterns and make accurate predictions from large amounts of data. The ability of machines to analyse and understand complex data has become an essential tool in the management of emergency situations, where quick and accurate decision-making can make the difference between life and death.

However, the quality and accuracy of these machine learning algorithms are highly dependent on the quality and diversity of the dataset on which they are trained. An insufficient or biased dataset can lead to inaccurate results and suboptimal decisions. This is where the fundamental purpose of this deliverable comes into play: to design, collect, analyse, and label a high-quality dataset that supports the machine learning capabilities of VALKYRIES.

The task of designing a suitable dataset for VALKYRIES is of the utmost importance, as it will serve as the basis on which the machine learning models will be built and trained. This involves not only the careful selection of the types of data to be included, such as geospatial information, climate data, records of past events, among others, but also ensuring that these data are representative and unbiased.

In addition, a thorough analysis of the collected data was performed to understand its distribution, trends, and potential challenges. This allow the identification of hidden patterns and characteristics crucial for emergency response operations.

Data tagging is another critical stage, as it involves assigning labels or categories to the data so that machine learning algorithms can learn and make accurate predictions. This process must be carried out accurately and consistently, avoiding any bias or error that could compromise the effectiveness of the models.

In summary, this project promoted by the European Union called Horizon Europe (1) promises to significantly improve emergency response operations by providing a high quality dataset for VALKYRIES machine learning techniques. In doing so, we aim to contribute to the advancement of this important field and have a positive impact on society by improving the ability to anticipate and respond to emergency situations, which can ultimately save lives and preserve safety in our communities.

3.1. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results (Tested before and during the project)
REQ_BASE_T7.2_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	Work has been made on study datasets to create a Valkyries-compatible model and they will be presented on M24 D7.2 Datasets Management and Benchmarking
REQ_BASE_T7.2_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	Generation of datasets with data from different perspectives serving as a reference for the SIGRUN framework is being made during integration tests M18.
REQ_BASE_T7.2_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	RECOMMENDED	Obtain information from virtual sensors to be concreted.
REQ_BASE_T7.2_4	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	Description of the dataset containing the minimum data with relevant information was made before the integration tests.
REQ_BASE_T7.2_5	P1	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	Extract the most relevant and discriminating features from the minimum dataset is being made during the integration of the tools.
REQ_BASE_T7.2_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	RECOMMENDED	The comparison between the datasets obtained and those already existing in the literature will be made after the first pilot.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results (Tested before and during the project)
REQ_COM_T7.2_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	SIGRUN system unifies the different data into one model offering support for the decision-making process during an emergency.
REQ_COM_T7.2_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	The system during the integration tests guaranteed treatment optimisation and increasing efficiency.
REQ_COM_T7.2_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	Models developed to detect and represent patients' status by analysing the various bio signals of the patients based on the triage phase.
REQ_COM_T7.2_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	OPTIONAL	Not implemented yet the reinforcement learning mechanisms to acquire new intelligence from past experiences.
REQ_COM_T7.2_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	REQUIRED	Employment of datasets from previous simulations, and other relevant data sources to train the models and to improve the existing ones.
REQ_COM_T7.2_6	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	RECOMMENDED	The integration of the models with existing software solutions for simulations will be made on M20.
REQ_COM_T7.2_7	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3	D7.2	OPTIONAL	Not implemented yet the acquisition of the most

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results (Tested before and during the project)
		VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9			relevant patterns from the data to train the learning models efficiently.
REQ_COM_T7.2_8	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D7.2	OPTIONAL	Not implemented yet the efficient labelling mechanisms.

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix

4. Background

In data science, pre-processing is essential to ensure the quality of the results. This section delve into the fundamentals of understanding datasets, cleaning data, applying transformations, and addressing imbalance, as well as the importance of visualisation. These processes are key to ensuring that data is fit and representative, allowing for accurate analysis and reliable conclusions at all stages of data analysis.

4.1. Fundamentals of datasets

4.1.1. Definition

The definition for dataset has changed over time, originally having a similar meaning to the word “file” (2). Although each of the sources (3), (4), (5), (6) and (2) tries to provide its own interpretation, for our case, we find appropriate to define it as a set of data elements that are of the same type and reflect the same characteristic of the objects for which they are collected. This implies that the objects in question possess the relevant characteristic. Examples of such characteristics may include temperature, shape, or appearance, among others. By type of the data elements, we mean the type of presentation of the information contained in them - numerical, textual, series, etc. and its dimensions - 1D/2D/nD.

Although data sets can be recorded on all kinds of media that mankind invented, these days, they are usually digitised and transferred to computer systems. So, from now on, when we talk about datasets, we mean a set of digitised data maintained in a computer system. In computer systems, the digitalised data sets are stored in organised logical and physical structures in the computer memory. Because it is tiered (L-xx cache, RAM, long-term storage), data representation suitable for each level is required. Therefore, the ability of the computer systems to execute instructions is used to transform the data between many physical and logical representations (tables/arrays, matrices, lists). This led to the invention of numerous complex forms of data organization for each memory tier. For example, while digitised images can be stored in random access memory as simple arrays of colour components, this is rarely used for long-term storage due to the space required. For practical reasons, images are stored compressed with a selected compression algorithm. The datasets are contained in one or more files in the long-term storage memory. These files are also organised and stored in physical form by computer operating systems in file systems, resulting in a hierarchical data organisation. Computer processing results in requirements at each level, along with the actual data, to create and store additional data (metadata) describing the data format.

Often, storing a single feature of an object is not enough to represent the object in the necessary detail, so multiple characteristics are used. When it is necessary to describe various relationships between objects based on multiple characteristics of them, the resulting datasets are grouped and stored together as a database. When the database is intended to be used for machine learning, in most cases, it is still referred to as a dataset. In other words, we can call a dataset or database a collection of data organized in some way for analysis. When the size of the database grows and fast access to its elements is required, indexing, compression, and partitioning techniques are applied. Specialized systems called database management systems can be used to outsource the associated complexity.

4.1.2. Application and types

Datasets are essential in many fields, such as science, data analysis, artificial intelligence, and programming in general.

The main purpose of a dataset is to provide a body of data that can be analysed to extract useful information. This information can be used to make strategic decisions and predictions, understand phenomena, test hypotheses, and other purposes. Specifically, datasets serve as the "raw material" for training models in artificial intelligence and machine learning.

The types of the datasets can be determined using many different criteria. For example, based on the area used as a source of information, they can be financial, geographical, geological, medical, demographic, logistical, historical, transportation, environmental, communication, social media, etc. Loosely based on the type of the data items and how they are processed, they can be textual, statistical (numeric), sound samples, images, and others.

In terms of size, datasets can be small or large (also known as "big data"). In terms of organization – structured, semi-structured and unstructured. Small datasets are manageable with standard data analysis tools, while large datasets require more advanced solutions. Structured datasets have a defined and organized format, while unstructured datasets can contain any data type without a clear organization. The semi-structured datasets, according to (7), can contain data that do not conform to the formal structure of data models (relational or other forms of data tables) but is somehow classified/tagged and has markers to separate semantic elements. In (8), a suitable example is given with company e-mails. The text is unstructured data, but mandatory fields include subject, sender, recipient, and headers.

Based on their temporal persistence, datasets can be static or dynamic. Static datasets remain unchanged over time, while dynamic datasets change and evolve. An example of a dynamic dataset is the financial data for the stock indices, obtained in real-time, and any other dataset that stores continuously incoming data.

The organization and structuring of the datasets also must be coherent representations of the world it aims to be used. So, different aspects of the world under analysis will require different dataset structures. As such, the metadata that supports the datasets plays a relevant role as it enables the coherence analysis to match the world being represented.

Diversity of datasets should provide a fair coverage of the world being represented, avoiding data bias due to the lack of representation. This is particularly relevant for training models with low supervision.

Another dimension to consider in the design of the datasets is its structure and complexity and the data volume it may require, considering the processing capacity and time response requirements. Failing to properly match the complexity and data volumes with the processing capacity and required time response will render unusable applicability of whatever decision-making is required.

4.2. Data cleaning

Data cleaning is an essential process in data analysis, but it is also a challenging process. It requires a solid understanding of the data and the potential errors and inconsistencies that can arise. However, despite these challenges, data cleaning is critical to ensure the quality of the data and the reliability of any analysis performed on it. Data cleaning, also known as data cleansing, is a fundamental phase in data analysis that focuses on identifying and correcting

errors and inconsistencies in a dataset. This process is essential to ensure the quality and accuracy of the data before its use for analysis and, therefore, to ensure the validity and reliability of the results.

The data cleaning process generally involves several steps. First, it is necessary to identify errors or inconsistencies in the data. These can be as simple as input errors (e.g., a misspelled name or incorrect date) or as complex as data collection discrepancies. Once these errors are identified, they must be corrected or eliminated. This may involve manual correction of errors, although, in larger datasets, automated tools are often used.

A trivial example of data cleaning in a dataset might be removing or correcting outliers. Outliers are values that deviate significantly from the typical range of values in a dataset. While in some cases, these values may be correct and provide valuable information, in others, they may result from errors and can distort the analysis results. This data processing type is particularly suitable if the data values are normally distributed.

A data cleaning process may involve the removal of duplicates. In some cases, data may be repeated in a dataset, which could distort the analysis results. In this case, duplicates should be identified and removed.

Removal of redundant elements can be applied to clean the data of non-descriptive features. For example, if HTML pages are collected for their text content, items like URLs, HTML tags, images, tracking codes, and counters should be removed to not interfere with the content.

Another example could be the interpolation (9) of missing data. There may be missing values due to errors in data collection or other reasons. In this case, replacing the missing data with a calculated value based on other available data is possible. For example, the elevation values obtained by satellite imagery might contain gaps or overlapped areas. Techniques that calculate the missing value using several nearby points and the information about the distances to apply weighted sum exist.

Data consistency is also a major concern in data cleaning. If data from different sources are being combined, there may be inconsistencies in how the data are collected or recorded. For example, one source may record dates in the "dd/mm/yyyy" format, while another may use the "mm/dd/yyyy" format. In this case, additional knowledge about the dataset can be applied. For example, it is known that the data is collected in an ordered manner along the time axis. In that case, we can implement logic to look for sudden forward/backward steps about the neighbour values on the same axis and try combinations m/d/y, d/m/y, or y/d/m, which satisfy the given threshold.

If the data represents some signal, then techniques for signal filtering might be applied so the desired signals are extracted from the noise. Echo cancelation is also a useful technique that improves the clarity of speech that contains mixed-in echo.

There are scenarios where there is metadata available which can be used to perform sophisticated filtering. For example, if there is an image dataset with people faces and metadata with their birth date and date of photo shooting like EXIF (10) are present, the images of given identity can be processed with apparent age recognizing machine learning (ML) model with known confidence. The confidence can be used to calculate the threshold/error margin value for each image. Any images that test and are firmly outside of the error margin can be considered either as images of another person or wrongly dated/labelled.

Another complex case is using a machine model to filter datasets so another model could be trained. For example, a trained text feature-extracting model can be used to flag texts for which the generated features show, for example, that contain hate speech so a bigger, explainable language model cannot be trained on them or be trained to recognize them and for example explain why they are inappropriate.

From the above, data cleaning is an essential process in data analysis, but it is also a challenging process. It requires a solid understanding of the data and the potential errors and inconsistencies that can arise. These inconsistencies must be resolved before the data can be analysed.

4.3. Data transformations

4.3.1. Introduction and definition

Data transformation refers to the process by which the data is converted from one format to another so that it can be ready for any specific purpose. The transformation aims to set the data provided by different sources, in different formats, from different references and scales, into a common reference and format so that any application knows how to interpret and read such data.

It usually requires some cleaning and removing not required content, when applicable. It may also require data enrichment by aggregating data from complementary sources.

So, the rules, steps, and algorithms are key for a good quality of the data resulting from a transformation process. For example, converting units (from yards to m) with a wrong conversion factor will make the data wrongly transformed and the datasets with low quality.

Data transformation processes can be simple or very effort, time, and resources demanding, depending on the purpose, volumes, and available data sources.

There are various data transformation methods, including the following:

- Aggregation, in which data is collected from multiple sources and stored in a single format.
- Attribute construction, in which new attributes are added or created from existing attributes.
- Discretization, which involves converting continuous data values into sets of data intervals with specific values to make the data more manageable for analysis.
- Generalization, where low-level data attributes are converted into high-level data attributes (for example, converting data from multiple brackets broken up by ages into the more general "young" and "old" attributes) to gain a more comprehensive view of the data.
- Integration, a step that involves combining data from different sources into a single view.
- Manipulation, where the data is changed or altered to make it more readable and organized.
- Normalization, a process that converts source data into another format to limit the occurrence of duplicated data.
- Smoothing, which uses algorithms to reduce "noise" in data sets, thereby helping to identify trends more efficiently and effectively in the data.

As it was stated in 4.1.1, data transformations are essential in the process of data acquisition, data storage, and data retrieval process, especially when computer systems are involved. In computer systems, data is transformed from its representation on the storage media to its representation in the RAM each time it is used. This process does not lead to a change in the data values. It is applied transparently without the user realizing it, so we will narrow our review to the transformations done with user participation. These transformations change the data values and are applied by the user with the given purpose in mind.

According to (11), transformation is defined as performing mathematical operation on each observation. In the general case, the operation can be not strictly mathematical but algorithmic. For example, the image crop transformation is not mathematic, but can be described as an algorithm and can be referred to as to function.

Whether they lead to data loss, transformations can be classified as reversible and irreversible. To illustrate this, a transformation is described with its transformation function f . It transforms the data values so the new value $X_{new} = f(X)$. A transformation, defined with the transformation function f , is reversible if the inversion function f^{-1} exists and is defined for each value of X_{new} , so the original values X can be calculated from the new values X_{new} as $X = f^{-1}(X_{new})$. The transformation is irreversible if such a function cannot be defined/described. Some transformations can be reversed only if the transformation parameters are known. For example, if currency conversion is applied to financial data. The transformation is reversible if metadata about the exchange rate used is preserved; otherwise, it is not. Also, all transformations involving one type of subsampling are irreversible because part of the data is lost. Lossless transformations include transposing/reshaping/pivoting, Min-Max scaling (normalization), Z-score normalization, tokenization, and encoding. Lossy transformations include image compression (using algorithms such as JPEG), quantization, dynamic range reduction, image distortions, denoising, all operations with images where crop operation is used to preserve rectangular output (e.g., rotation, perspective, and lens correction), feature extraction, and dimensionality reduction. Mathematically, lossless transformations may lead to some precision loss due to the finite precision of the presentation of the floating-point numbers in the computer systems.

4.3.2. Details and examples.

Data transformations are applied to prepare the data for further analysis or to be made usable by a predefined model or system. Data augmentations are a case of lossy data transformations where the original data items remain unaltered. They are often used to generate additional data points from the existing ones for the needs of machine learning algorithms. The goal is to improve the generalization performance of the ML models when the training dataset is not big enough, for example, when adding new samples is expensive.

Normalization (Min-Max scaling) (12). Normalization is the first and most used form of data transformation, also known as Min-Max scaling. It applies to data that contains numbers. For example, if the data comprises sound samples (series), collected with variation on the recording volume, we may want to normalize it. The algorithm is as follows:

1. The dataset is traversed to find the maximal and minimal values X_{max} and X_{min}
2. The amplitude is calculated: $amplitude = X_{max} - X_{min}$
3. The normalized dataset values X' are derived using the following transformation equation:

$$X_{norm}^i = \frac{X^i - X_{min}}{\text{amplitude}}$$

The resulting X_{norm} values fit into the [0; 1] range. We will illustrate the effect of normalization on the dataset in (13). It contains data for three wine classes, and for each class, there are multiple samples taken. Suppose the goal is to train a classifier to distinguish between the three classes of wine based on the content of alcohol and malic acid. However, since the alcohol values in the dataset vary between 11.03 % and 14.83% and the malic acid content between 0.74 % and 5.80 %, our two features are not on an equal scale. This makes it difficult to use the features directly. To be able to use them without deriving special weighting functions, normalization can be applied. After normalization, the values of both malic acid and alcohol fall into the range [0; 1], so we can use a standard loss function.

While the Min-Max scaling is a good way to put different variables in the same dimension, it is sensitive to outliers, which can change the scale for other data in the dataset. The Z-score normalization is less sensitive to outliers. The Z-score normalized data has a mean value of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. To calculate Z-score, the following algorithm can be used:

1. Find the mean value, μ of the dataset.
2. Calculate the standard deviation of the dataset.
3. Calculate Z-score for i^{th} data point.

The Z-score compared to the Min-Max scaled values can be negative. There are transformations that are primarily used in certain sectors due to the nature of the data collected. According (11), the most common non-linear transformations, used in the biology are Log transformation, Square-root transformation, and Arcsine transformation.

The Log (Logarithmic) transformation uses logarithm function with base 10 or natural logarithm (base e). The usage in biology is justified with the fact that many variables in the biology have log-normal distributions (11). This means that after applying a logarithmic transformation, these variables are distributed according to the normal law. If there are negative numbers, the dataset must be offset by addition of a positive constant to all values.

The Square-root transformation consists of taking the square root of each (11). Both Logarithmic and Square-root transformations reduce the impact of the outlier values.

Encoding. Often, the data is represented in categories/classes rather than with numbers. These classes have text names and must be presented with numbers because the ML algorithms cannot handle textual descriptions directly. For example, suppose a dataset contains names of different species like elephants, gorillas, and chickens. In that case, they can get categorical encoding, where a discrete integer number is set for each name: Chicken=> 1, Elephant=>2, Gorilla=>3, etc.

Another kind of transformation is **Data Discretization**. It is used to reduce the number of possible values to ease the processing and understanding of the data. For example, when there is a dataset with many people, we must work with their ages. Age is a continuous variable, and it can take many values. It can be transformed from a continuous to a discrete variable with several categorical values (based on predefined intervals), for example, Kid [4-11], Teenager [12-18], Young [19-30], Middle aged [31-45] and Senior [50+]. The discretization is a lossy process.

Dimensionality reduction (14) is another technique, close to Data discretization, because it also loses data and simplifies it, so the automatic processing goes faster. There is a known problem

called the “curse of the dimensions,” which refers to the difficulty of searching in high-dimensional spaces (15). The effort to search increases exponentially with the linear growth of dimensions (16). So, when dimensionality reduction is implemented, the goal is to sustain maximum information about features while reducing the number of attributes (e.g., dimensions). For this purpose, many transformations/projections have been invented. For example, the Karhunen-Loeve transformation (17) can be used for dimensionality reduction. It is also often called Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (18) for discrete data cases. The fact that the finite-term Karhunen-Loeve expansion is optimal regarding the mean-square error (19) implies that it can be used to search for compact representation of higher dimensionality data. A simpler and less demanding algorithm for dimensionality reduction of hyperspectral images, called Discrete Prolate Spheroidal Sequences (DPSS), is proposed in (20), which implies that it can be used to search for compact representation of higher dimensionality data. A simpler and less demanding algorithm for dimensionality reduction of hyperspectral images, called Discrete Prolate Spheroidal Sequences (DPSS), is proposed in (21), a machine-learning-based algorithm for dimensionality reduction of HS images called “Spatial-spectral manifold reconstruction preserving embedding” (SSMRPE) is proposed and evaluated against PCA, NPE, LPP, LDA, LFDA, SC-NPE, DSSMs and LPNPE algorithms, where it outperforms them. It uses a new metric, called spatial-spectral combined distance (SSCD), to learn how to combine the spatial and spectral information in spatio-spectral neighbouring pixels.

Other techniques for dimensionality reduction are Backward feature elimination (BFE), Forward feature selection (FFS), Missing value ratio, Low variance filter, High correlation filter, Decision trees, Random forest, General discriminant analysis (GDA), and Semi-supervised GDA. Some of them are described in (22). The Backward feature elimination and Forward feature selection techniques perform feature filtering. The FFS starts with zero selected features and tries to find the most representative features by adding them individually and evaluating the performance with the feature set. If the recently added feature improves the results, it is kept. It is discarded. This way, only the representative features are selected. This is only a high-level description of this technique. As its name states, the BFE eliminates the features one by one. It searches for the least representative feature and then drops it. The performance/selectivity of the model/system is evaluated until all features whose loss does not contribute significantly to performance loss are eliminated. The Missing value ratio approach is quite simple – features with the most missing values (when the dataset is incomplete) are dropped. It works with thresholds for missing values and is not applicable for datasets where all values are present.

The low variance filter features a filter that calculates the variance of a given dimension (column). Based on this, it accepts as a parameter threshold value of the variance and drops the columns with low variance based on the expectation that they do not contain much information.

The high correlation filter calculates the correlation between different dimensions (source and target), and where it finds a high correlation, it drops the target dimension based on the assumption that it contains redundant information already contained in the source dimension.

The General discriminant analysis (GDA) is a dimensionality reduction algorithm whose goal is to find a nonlinear projection that simultaneously maximizes the between-class dissimilarity and minimizes the within-class dissimilarity to increase class reparability (discrimination) (23). As the improvement of GDA for working with unlabelled data, the study in (23) proposes the Semi-supervised GDA algorithm. Dimensionality reduction can also be done with training for specific data ML feature-extracting models, as shown in (24).

Data compression is another form of data transformation. It can be lossless (for example, Huffman coding, arithmetic coding) or lossy when (DCT, Wavelet, KLT) decomposition and coefficients/components reduction are applied. Most often, lossy compression is applied to 2D images, but studies like (25), show that it can also be extended to volumetric data. In (25), experiments were conducted with the representation of volumetric data of a human liver using several different techniques (pyramid, KLT, and 3D DCT). The DCT transformation, while inferior, was found to be a close approximation of the KLT transformation. The research reduced the storage space required to 5 % of the original. The lossless compression typically yields a much lower compression ratio, but still, it reduces the cost of storing datasets while preserving all data. This is done via optimal coding, using the fact that there are repeating fragments in the digital representation of the data.

Derivation is a technique of using the existing metrics to create a new one. For example, a column “Profit” can be created when from column “Income,” the columns “Taxes” and “External Service fees” are subtracted. In some cases, the annotation can be viewed as a derivation. It is a process of labelling (extracting clean features from the data) and appending annotations as additional data (or metadata) for reinforcement learning. For example, on an image that contains cars, the annotation might be to draw a contour around each car instance and label it as a car.

Translation and mapping must be applied if datasets containing relevant data in different formats (e.g., JSON texts and XML texts) need to be combined. The tag names for the same contents might differ, which requires mapping one field name to another.

Data anonymization is a technique used when a data set containing personal data is to be released, for example, for scientific research. Because the recent legislation forbids the data of non-public people to be shared, the sensitive elements can be replaced with machine-generated substitutions. For example, instead of Juan Carlos, the name can be substituted with Male000. Among the data transformations used to augment the data in the training of models that process images are scale, shear, crop, perspective correction, rotation, horizontal and vertical shift, horizontal and vertical flip, blur, motion blur, median blur, sharpening, random brightness and contrast, centre crop, grid distortion, HSV variation, additive Gaussian noise, Gaussian noise, resize, channel dropout, coarse dropout, add rain, add snow, mix-up, and others. Typically, these transformations use randomly generated parameters to cause non-repeating data variations during training. An example of a few image data transformations is shown in Figure 1.

A grid is mixed in the image for better visualization of affine transformations, which are harder to be detected by the naked eye.

Figure 1 - Some image data transformations using a lion image

4.4. Unbalanced data

A dataset is imbalanced if the classification categories are not approximately equally represented (26). The effects of using imbalanced datasets on training classifiers are discussed in (27), with conclusions drawn that the overwhelming presence of the samples of majority classes leads to classifiers that ignore the minority classes. Usage of (less) unbalanced data can also lead to biased models. This is especially important when training machine learning models designed for law enforcement. For example, when in the USA, a face recognition machine model was trained to infer the probability of a given person being a wanted criminal based on a comparison of the facial features, the model was giving far more false positives on facial images depicting darker skin tones and females as compared to facial images depicting Caucasian males (28). The imbalanced dataset used in the training was the reason for such performance. According to (29), the dataset used to train facial recognition technology lacked sufficient samples of black people and females. This led to a biased model that could not distinguish well between a black suspect and a black person currently being checked. The problem of biased datasets is not limited to facial recognition technology but also affects algorithms intended to provide hate speech classification for the automated censorship systems in social networks, as shown in (30) and machine learning models with medical applications. Research articles dedicated to medical image analysis state that an imbalanced dataset causes hindrances in training and is driving the training towards overfitting (31). Therefore, techniques to eliminate or reduce the negative effects must be implemented.

The methods for diminishing the effect of using imbalanced training, proposed in (31), are focused on equalization as much as possible of the number of the data samples between all classes and assigning weights to the different classes so the loss of the model to be optimized in the desired direction. In (32), the researchers were working on reducing the bias in hate speech detection models used to support automated censorship implemented in the social network they work for. They introduced the “dialect and race priming” technique. It consists of appending additional labels to the data, indicating the source race and language of the comments to contextualize the text samples. Suppose the language is African American dialect, or the source person is African American, and the tweets are related to mentioning certain

phrases otherwise considered offending to black people. In that case, the loss function considers it and reduces the likelihood of this being detected as hate speech. This reduced the false positives by about 11% because these phrases are more likely to be used in a humorous context. While race priming might show better results in experiments with African-American language, it cannot be used as a “one solution fits it all” because, as a form of racial discrimination technique (detecting race and background of a person, not to be misinterpreted as violation of rights), it can lead to equality violations against all other races, for example when the source person is black but the target person is not.

When the imbalance is in terms of the number of presented instances of a given class in the dataset, undersampling is one of the first and easiest techniques to implement. It consists of approaches to reduce the number of samples present for the majority class. There are various approaches: random undersampling, boundary undersampling, and others. The cons of this technique are that it causes data loss, and by reducing samples, we reduce the variety in the dataset, so important features might be omitted. To avoid data loss, oversampling techniques are proposed. Instead of deleting samples representing the majority class, the oversampling techniques suggest artificially increasing minority classes. The simplest technique is to duplicate samples of the minority class. They differ by the sample selection criteria; the simplest is random sampling. More sophisticated techniques were developed to improve the quality of the resulting datasets instead of duplicating samples. In (33) the researchers applied the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) to investigate the effect of balancing on the performance of various ML models in the healthcare domain. While it did not improve the performance of all models, the training using the balanced via SMOTE dataset significantly improved the performance of the best-performing models compared to the imbalanced dataset. The SMOTE technique itself was suggested in (26). It consists of the application of appropriate for the type of training data augmentations to data samples from the minority classes, so new, slightly different synthetic samples are generated and added to the dataset to equalize the number of samples of all classes. This is called upsampling/oversampling of the minority class. Studies have shown that this technique yields better results than simply repeating/duplicating data. An improved variant, called Density-Based Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique (DBSMOTE), is presented in (34). It imposes rules to generate the synthetic samples for the minority class so that their features are close to the “centre of the mass” of the features of all samples for this class. According to the article (34). It imposes rules to generate the synthetic samples for the minority class so that their features are close to the “centre of the mass” of the features of all samples for this class. According to the article (34), DBSMOTE improves the precision of the trained model, compared to SMOTE, Borderline-SMOTE, and Safe-Level-SMOTE. Some studies propose a combined approach, which consists of implementing oversampling techniques to increase the number of samples of the minority class and undersampling techniques to the majority class samples. To achieve additional benefits, e.g., reduce the noise, selective undersampling, which removes the outliers, might be applied. Depending on the nature of the data, some synthesis techniques might prove difficult or impossible to implement. Hence, selecting the synthesis method is an important part of the development process. In the survey in (35), some methods rely on specifically trained GAN models to facilitate samples synthesis.

Later, algorithms that perform guided oversampling and balancing, like ADASYN, were suggested. The ADASYN algorithm combines techniques for dynamic adjustment of weights and estimation of the data distributions to provide an adaptive learning procedure (36). The part of

the algorithm that selects samples of the minority class as a base for synthetic oversampling is tuned to prefer these, which are harder to learn by the ML model.

There are also developed methods for fighting the negative effects of imbalanced datasets without balancing them. For example, different sampling methods perform balanced sample selection (e.g., class weighting) during the ML training phase. Other methods rely on redesigning the loss functions, which are used for training the model to provide balancing via loss weighting. For the case of binary classification, the weights can be inversely proportional to the number of training samples of each class. For example, the weight for the i -th class can be calculated as:

$$W_{cl_i} = \frac{nSamplesTot}{nSamples_{cl_i} * nClasses}$$

The number of all samples in the dataset is the number of the samples of the i -th class and the number of the classes. As it can be seen, on prediction error, the minority class error will be taken with higher weight than the majority class error, which, given the higher probability of the sample to be of the majority class, will try to equalize (long term) the effect on the trained weights of the ML model. This solution is not optimal because the amount the model weights will be updated depends on its state and whether the model will recognize the specific training sample. So, research works applying more sophisticated weighting are developed. For example, an adaptive weighting scheme that considers prediction scores during training is proposed in (37).

Conclusion: From the literature study, it was found that the use of an imbalanced dataset for training ML models is a challenging task. Applying suitable data types and training procedure balancing techniques is crucial to obtaining well-performing ML models. They can be implemented as weighting in the loss function, as guided real-time sample selection and synthesis (oversampling) procedures, or as balancing applied on the dataset before the training process. The specific use case might require research on which technique will give the best-performing model.

4.5. Data visualization

4.5.1. Definition

Data visualization is a set of techniques used to present the data with graphics intended to be perceived by human visual organs. The graphics consist of visual primitives. The difficulty and, accordingly, the time required for human perception of graphics is proportional to their complexity. The amount of graph primitives determines the complexity of graphs in them. The information carried in a graph of a given type is proportional to the amount of graph primitives in it. As an immediate example, the written speech in this document can be given - the number of letters (each composed of graphic primitives) in the document is proportional to the amount of information in it. From the above, it can be concluded that data visualization faces the problem of conveying more useful information with fewer graphic primitives. This problem is solved by answering which aspects/characteristics of the available data are the most important for the current case and how to present them in the simplest perception form. This way, a visualization type is selected, or a new one is developed (if needed) on a case-by-case basis. It works because the right visualization filters out unnecessary features, allowing the human brain to access the important information needed to solve the case as quickly as possible. The text is a universal way for graphical representation of the speech, and it is not specialized for a given

case; thus, potentially, it is among the suboptimal (in terms of speed and amount of brain activity required) ways of presenting the relevant features of the data. For the visualization, the goal determines the method. Because developing new types of visualization requires much creativity, it could be argued that visualization is a form of art. From another viewpoint, visualization development is a science because it requires deep knowledge of the relations between human perception and cognitive abilities and is part of cognitive ergonomics. Because a given type of visualization often applies to similar cases and its development costs much effort, it is expedient to be reused many times. Using computers, the visualization types can be parametrized and reused. Software libraries like (38) and data visualization tools have been created to provide implementations for big amount of the already invented visualization types.

Use cases vs. types. As stated earlier, the visualizations are created according to the use case. There are use cases where only a preview of the data is needed for verification, for example, to check whether the data is read/written correctly by the data gathering process or to inspect a data sample at different stages of the data transformation process. In these cases, only a small portion of the data is visualized. The case-specific aspect is to present the data as is at the given step, so the most appropriate visualization types are non-aggregating – detailed table (for numeric/text data) or 2D/3D image (if the data contains images) as in Figure 1 are enough. Non-aggregation visualizations also apply in cases where certain data elements are searched for in a dataset for reporting needs (for example, retrieving a row by one of the columns). In practice, non-aggregating visualizations are used less often, as they do not reveal the power of visualizations to summarize large volumes of information in a single frame. Examples of aggregation visualizations are charts/diagrams for visualizing statistical information, for example, the distribution of elements of each class in each data set. There are many types of charts invented: bar charts, line charts, pie charts and their nested variants, box plots, violin plots, and bubble charts, to name but a few. Because of the wide variety of visualizations available, like those in (38), (39), only a small sample of all types is illustrated below. While bar charts are good for the presentation of statistical data, when the accent is on the percentage of the whole, the circular/pie charts seem to be a better choice. Examples of circular charts are given in Figure 2.

For cases when 3D data must be visualized, the 3rd dimension can be presented via colour mapping on 2D plot or by using 3D projection. Several suitable types of visualizations for 3D data are shown at Figure 3. Data and code are adapted from (40) and (41).

For use cases, where the user needs to drill through the data, interactive visualizations are developed. They have controls that respond to user actions and allow them to browse the data.

There exist more complex visualizations which leverage the stereovision of the human beings. They require special kits for perception like stereo goggles and armbands on the hands to detect the motion in the 3D space so to provide navigation. Some interfaces provide augmented reality, where the visualizations are augmenting the real world with additional artefacts/controls or information.

Figure 2 - Examples of visualizations with circular diagrams

Figure 3 - Examples of visualizations of 3D data

4.5.2. Tools for visualizations.

There exist many libraries and tools (applications) that provide visualization functionality. The goals and the use case should determine the selection of the right tool. The most available applications are installed on almost every desktop computer in the "Office suite" category. It can be Microsoft Office, Open Office, Libre Office, or Calligra. At a minimum, the capabilities of the included software, in addition to their formats, allow reading datasets in CSV format and performing visualizations. In most cases, the applications are also scriptable – and can be extended with scripts. However, the office applications have limitations. Typically, these applications are not well optimized for handling large datasets that cannot fit in the system memory. At the disposal of the data, scientists are powerful and open-source visualization libraries like Matplotlib (38). For visualization of static or dynamic data on the Web, there are JavaScript libraries like D3 (42), Chartjs (43), Highcharts (44), Victory (45), ReCharts (46) and others. The JavaScript-based libraries allow user interactions with the graphics like zooming, moving, and others. They need support with compatible interface on the backend, where the data resides, such as Elastic Search or another.

For the analysts of business data, there are powerful business intelligence tools like PowerBi (47), Oracle Bi (48) and others. Tools such as Tableau (49), Infogram (50), Datawrapper (51) and others are available to support big data analysis.

Data visualization has many applications – when datasets are prepared for analysis, the data visualization helps to find outliers. Also, it helps to visually navigate the data (if it is made interactive).

Data visualization is a key process of the decision-making chain and of the users to understand the decision context and to properly assess the decision environment and the options scenarios, either at the operational, tactical, or strategic level.

Data visualization also depends on the time nature of the data, whether static or dynamic data and the updating time rate of the dynamical data, which, favourably, should be done in the time that allows the decision-making process.

The data visualization also considers the format and nature of the data sources: text, image, picture, video, or data structure and metadata. The layout for visualization required context visualization, such as maps, geographical coordinates, data sequencing visualization, timely ordered, etc.

An example of the visualization tools explored in VALKYRIES is the GLOBAL COP, where the data is organized and displayed. Such visualization tools should also consider the user experience to prevent misinterpretation of the data, user fatigue, and data completeness to support the decision-maker / operator. For that purpose, the colour pallet and significance used in the visualization should also be standardized and of clear interpretation.

Finally, the data extracted or fusioned in a visualization tool should allow the user to decompose the aggregated/fusion data source components for further analysis.

Data visualization is also a key process of the decision-making chain of the users. It allows them to understand the decision context and to properly assess the decision environment and the options scenarios, either at the operational, tactical, or strategic level.

Data visualization also depends on the data's time nature - static or dynamic. When the data is dynamic, the use case might require the updating rate to be done within a certain time, allowing for timely decisions.

The format and nature of the data sources (text, image, pictures, video, data structure, and metadata) also determine the possibilities of applying one type of visualization. The layout for visualization might require context, such as maps for geographical coordinates, data sequencing visualization to be timely ordered, etc.

Examples of the visualization tools explored in VALKYRIES is the GLOBAL COP, where the data is organized and displayed. Such visualization tools should also consider the user experience to prevent misinterpretation of the data, user fatigue, and data completeness to support the decision-maker/operator. For that purpose, the colour pallet and significance used in the visualization should also be standardized and of clear interpretation.

Finally, the data extracted in a visualization tool, should, optimally should allow the user to decompose the aggregated data source components for further analysis.

4.5.3. Conclusion.

There are various visual primitives to represent data. While the tabular format directly corresponds with the numeric data, it is the hardest to understand because it does not allow for easy conclusions or assessments. Other forms like charts, maps, and graphs allow the power of data visualization to provide single-page images, allowing the human being to conclude thousands of data records quickly. Among the drawbacks of data visualization is that it can be deceptive, depending on the scale applied (particularly the nonlinear scales) or offset. Examples can be seen when the performance of processors is compared at some sites where differences

under 2-3% are extended to look much bigger visually, either by changing the scale to nonlinear or by starting the bars from a given number instead of zero.

5. State of the art

In the field of emergency research, the availability of appropriate datasets is critical to developing effective models and strategies. This section will examine the state of the art in relation to datasets used in emergency situations. Issues such as the diversity of data sources, the breadth of scenarios covered, and collection methodologies will be addressed. A detailed review of these datasets will provide insight into how the scientific community approaches the representation of critical situations, facilitating the evaluation and improvement of response and recovery strategies in such contexts.

5.1. Triage datasets

First, in this subsection, a review of the literature related to triage datasets has been carried out.

5.1.1. Title: Emergency Service Triage

Study Explanation: This retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted between October 2016 and September 2017, encompassing the selection of 1267 adult patient records from two emergency services. A total of 24 variables were evaluated, including primary complaints, vital signs, and clinical outcomes.

Study Analysis: The study comprehensively addresses various medical facets by examining these variables. The systematic record selection enhances result validity. The involvement of triage experts ensures the accuracy of the KTAS assessment, potentially exerting a substantial impact on emergency medical care and triage procedures. This study provides a profound insight into emergency medical care and may influence enhancements in clinical decision-making and resource allocation.

5.1.2. Triage Accuracy and Causes of Mis triage using the Korean Triage and Acuity Scale

Study Explanation: The study focuses on evaluating the accuracy of the triage process in emergency services using the Korean Triage and Acuity Scale (KTAS). It also examines why errors occur in this process.

Methods Employed: A total of 1267 records of adult patients in emergency services between October 2016 and September 2017 were analysed. Twenty-four variables, including chief complaints and vital signs, were evaluated. Three triage experts compared actual KTAS scores with those of emergency nurses. The causes of triage errors were studied. The study also analysed whether there were differences in the number of patients attended per hour between accurate and inaccurate triage assessments.

Study Results: There was high agreement between KTAS scores assigned by emergency nurses and experts ($\kappa = 0.83$, Pearson = 0.88, $p < 0.001$). Of 1267 records, 186 displayed triage disagreement (131 under triaged, 55 over triaged). Primary error causes included incorrect application of the numerical rating scale ($n = 64$) and erroneous judgment of physical symptoms ($n = 47$). There was no significant difference in the number of patients attended per hour between accurate and inaccurate triage assessments.

Study Conclusions: High concordance was found between KTAS scores assigned by emergency nurses and experts. Triage errors were primarily attributed to mistakes in applying the pain scale and interpreting physical symptoms.

Explanation of Study Parameters: Significantly high agreement between scores assigned by emergency nurses and experts when using the Korean Triage and Acuity Scale (KTAS).

- Kappa (κ) = 0.83: The kappa value is an indicator of agreement between two evaluators. In this case, a value of 0.83 indicates substantial agreement, implying significant alignment between scores given by emergency nurses and experts.
- Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) = 0.88: The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the relationship between two datasets. A value of 0.88 suggests a strong positive correlation, indicating that the scores assigned by emergency nurses and experts were closely related to each other.
- $p < 0.001$: This "p" value is an indicator of statistical significance. A value less than 0.001 means that the probability of this high KTAS score concordance being due to chance is extremely low. In other words, it is highly likely that this concordance is real and not a random result.

Collectively, these results indicate that emergency nurses and experts evaluated similarly using the KTAS Scale, and this concordance is not due to chance but is statistically significant.

5.1.3. Patient Priority for Clustering

VALKYRIES project also focuses on providing triage. Triage refers to sorting injured or sick people according to their need for emergency medical attention. Triage prioritizes patient care (or victims during a disaster) based on illness/injury, symptoms, severity, prognosis, and resource availability. Database Patient Priority for Clustering is based on patient symptoms, identifying patients needing immediate resuscitation, assigning patients to a predesignated patient care area, thereby prioritizing their care, and initiating diagnostic/therapeutic measures as appropriate.

5.2. Natural disaster datasets

Finally, in this subsection, the literature related to natural disaster datasets, like fires, earthquakes, or COVID-19, has been reviewed.

5.2.1. FDNY Firehouse Listing

Study Explanation: NYC Open Data constitutes a government-driven initiative by the City of New York to afford open and accessible access to data generated and employed by the government for all residents. The primary mission is to stimulate citizen engagement by enabling New Yorkers to interact with governmental information and employ it meaningfully.

Study Analysis: The emphasis on open data by NYC Open Data underscores the commitment of the New York government to transparency and the democratization of information. By rendering key governmental data available, an opportunity arises for citizens to partake in informed decision-making and oversight of governmental operations. The presence of a dedicated team and an emphasis on collaboration with municipal agencies underscores the significance accorded to data quality and accessibility. Open Data Coordinators within each agency ensure effective communication and proper dataset management. The mention of the civic tech community and its support demonstrates the bidirectional interaction between government and society. This collaboration reinforces open data's value in ameliorating New Yorkers' quality of life and crafting innovative solutions that address the city's challenges.

5.2.2. OSHA Accident and Injury Data

Study Explanation: This dataset presents information on natural disasters and emergencies in the United States since 1953. It is compiled by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and is regularly updated. The data encompasses details regarding various types of disasters, including hurricanes, wildfires, and the response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Study Analysis: The dataset allows for opportunities to analyse trends over time in terms of the frequency and severity of natural disasters. It also enables the evaluation of seasonal and geographical patterns. Furthermore, the subset tailored for the M5 Forecasting competition offers the potential to develop forecasting models capable of predicting the occurrence of future disasters. Collectively, this dataset is indispensable for understanding how to confront and mitigate the impacts of natural disasters and emergencies in the United States.

5.2.3. US Natural Disaster Declarations

Study Explanation: This dataset aggregates information concerning natural disaster declarations in the United States, encompassing hurricanes, wildfires, and the COVID-19 pandemic. It is managed by the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and is regularly updated to reflect current and past events. The data provides an overview of federal government-issued disaster declarations since 1953. The data has been processed to enhance its quality and format. A subset of data tailored for the M5 Forecasting competition is also provided.

Study Analysis: This dataset permits analyses to understand the frequency and types of disasters impacting the United States. It can aid in identifying temporal, geographical, and economic patterns associated with natural disasters. Furthermore, the subset for the M5 Forecasting competition offers the opportunity to develop predictive models that anticipate future disaster declarations, thereby contributing to improved preparedness and emergency response.

5.2.4. NYC OEM Emergency Notifications

Study Explanation: This dataset comprises messages dispatched by the Office of Emergency Management (OEM) of New York. These messages convey information concerning emergency events and vital services. The data forms a part of the city's open data platform and is updated as new data is entered. The dataset encompasses OEM messages from New York that furnish critical information about emergencies and key services.

Study Analysis: The dataset affords the opportunity to analyse how the city responds to emergencies and communicates information to its citizens. Patterns in the frequency and types of notifications can be discerned, and the effectiveness of emergency communication can be evaluated. This analysis could significantly enhance critical situation planning and response within the city.

5.2.5. NY Emergency Response Incidents

Study Explanation: This dataset presents information about emergency incidents responded to by the Office of Emergency Management (OEM) of New York. The data includes incident types and associated addresses. The city hosts this data on its open data platform, which is periodically updated based on the influx of information. The dataset furnishes details regarding emergency incidents addressed by New York's OEM. This encompasses incident types and their corresponding addresses.

Study Analysis: These data enable the analysis of the most frequently responded to types of emergency incidents by the OEM. They can unveil patterns in incident location and nature. The monthly update frequency allows for tracking trends over time and assessing how the city responds to different emergency types. Such analyses can significantly improve preparedness and response to critical situations in New York.

5.2.6. Fire Incidents

Study Explanation: This dataset presents information concerning fire incidents in Toronto over nine years. The data originates from Toronto Fire Services (TFS), Canada's largest fire

department, providing fire protection and other emergency services. The dataset encompasses details about fire incidents in Toronto from 2011 to 2018. It includes pertinent information such as estimated dollar losses, location coordinates, and precise date and time for each incident.

Study Analysis: These data facilitate the analysis of trends in fire frequency over time and their geographical distribution. It is also possible to assess the economic impact of fires and comprehend potential causes. Such analysis can significantly enhance response planning and resource allocation for fire situations in Toronto.

5.2.7. Earthquakes

Study Explanation: This dataset delves into whether earthquakes can be interconnected and if one earthquake can trigger another. The author raises the question of whether larger earthquakes, with magnitudes exceeding 4, could be induced by other earthquakes. This curiosity has led to exploring the topic and investigating the feasibility of earthquake prediction. Predicting earthquakes is a complex challenge involving numerous parameters and sensor data. Most prediction efforts focus on alerting about earthquakes in the next few seconds, utilizing multiple instantly measured parameters to forecast whether an earthquake will occur shortly. As of September 2019, the accuracy of these predictions stood at 58% but has since improved to 84%. Emphasis is placed on short-term forecasting to alert individuals approximately 6 to 9 seconds before the earthquake.

Study Analysis: This dataset proves invaluable for analysing efforts in earthquake prediction and how accuracy has evolved. The emphasis on short-term prediction stands out, aiming to alert individuals just before an earthquake. Furthermore, the dataset may reveal distinctive features associated with earthquakes.

5.2.8. Natural Disasters 1900 – 2021

Study Explanation: The Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT) compiles information on over 22,000 mass disasters worldwide from 1900 to the present. It focuses on natural disasters and contains details about their occurrence and impacts. EM-DAT is constructed from data originating from diverse sources, including UN agencies, non-governmental organizations, and press agencies. This dataset provides valuable information for analysing the patterns of natural disasters over time and across different regions. Potential analyses include:

- Temporal Trends: Observing whether the frequency or severity of disasters has changed over the years.
- Prominent Locations: Identifying regions most susceptible to certain types of natural disasters.
- Types of Disasters: Categorizing disasters by type and examining whether specific types are more common than others.
- Human and Economic Impact: Evaluating the number of lives lost and the economic cost associated with these disasters.
- Response and Recovery: Investigating how communities have recovered from different types of disasters.
- Climate Change: Analysing whether there has been an increase in disaster frequency, possibly related to climate change.

5.2.9. Significant Earthquake Dataset 1900-2023

This dataset for 1900-2023 is a comprehensive collection of data on major earthquakes that have occurred worldwide over the past 123 years. It is regularly updated to provide accurate

and up-to-date information on earthquake events. The dataset includes information on over 37,000 earthquakes that have occurred in this period of 123 years. The dataset includes the earthquake's date, time, location, magnitude, and depth. This dataset is maintained by the US Geological Survey – National Earthquake Information Center.

This dataset is a valuable resource for seismologists, geologists and other researchers who study earthquakes and earth, as well as for emergency managers and other professionals – first responders who work in disaster response and preparedness.

5.3. Summary table

Dataset	Processing	Techniques Used	Purpose	Purpose in Emergency Situations
Emergency Service - Triage Application	Analysis of Emergency Department Patient Data	Statistical analysis, systematic selection of records, evaluation of KTAS	To provide an in-depth view of emergency medical care and improve clinical decision making and resource allocation.	Help medical professionals assess and prioritize patient care in emergency departments, which can have a significant impact on emergency medical care and triage processes.
FDNY Firehouse Listing	List of FDNY Fire Stations	Data extraction and information gathering	Provide useful information about FDNY fire stations in New York City.	Provide quick and accessible information on the locations of fire stations in New York City, which can be crucial for summoning help in case of fire or other related emergencies.
OSHA Accident and Injury Data	Information on accidents and injuries reported to OSHA	Statistical analysis, data collection	Provide information on workplace safety in the United States.	Identify patterns and trends in workplace accidents and injuries, which can help improve workplace safety and prevent future incidents in emergency situations.
US Natural Disaster Declarations	List of natural disaster declarations issued by the President of the United States.	Information gathering	Provide information on natural disasters in the United States.	Enable rapid identification of areas affected by natural disasters, which facilitates the coordination of response efforts and helps in the allocation of resources during emergency situations.
NYC OEM Emergency Notifications	Information on emergency notifications issued by the New York City OEM	Information gathering	Provide useful information on emergency notifications issued by OEM in New York City.	Keep residents informed of emergency notifications and alerts issued by the New York City Office of Emergency Management (OEM), which helps ensure a quick and efficient response to emergency situations.
NY Emergency Response Incidents	Information on incidents to which the New York Police Department (NYPD) responded.	Information gathering	Provide useful information about incidents to which the NYPD responded in New York.	Provide information on incidents to which the New York Police Department (NYPD) has responded, which can assist in the planning and coordination of response operations during emergency situations.

Fire incidents	Fire Incidents in Toronto	Data collection and statistical analysis	Provide useful information on fire incidents in Toronto.	To help understand the frequency, location, and characteristics of fires in Toronto, which can be useful in improving fire-related emergency prevention and response strategies.
Earthquakes	Earthquake Prediction	Statistical analysis, modelling, and forecasting	To provide useful information on the occurrence and prediction of earthquakes.	Provide information on earthquake prediction and monitoring, which can help in planning and preparing for emergency situations caused by earthquakes.

Table 2 - State of the art summary table

6. Valkyries approach

The creation of a multi-victim emergency dataset across different countries is a vitally important initiative in the field of emergency management and public health. Health emergencies, whether natural disasters, infectious disease outbreaks, major accidents, or any other catastrophic event, can have a devastating impact on the health and well-being of the population. In the face of these complex and challenging scenarios, having a complete and collaborative dataset becomes an invaluable tool for informed decision making and the creation of artificial intelligence models that automate critical processes.

The contextualisation of this need lies in the transnational nature of many health emergencies. Natural disasters, pandemics and other critical events know no borders and can affect multiple countries simultaneously. Collaboration between nations and coordination of efforts become essential for an effective response and to mitigate the effects of these incidents on the population. In this context, the creation of a shared dataset that stores detailed information on multi-victim emergencies between different countries becomes a crucial tool to improve joint preparedness and response.

Collecting and storing data from multiple countries in a single dataset is essential to obtain a global and holistic view of the situation. Information on available medical resources, the evolution of cases, response protocols, measures implemented, and results obtained, among others, allows for the analysis of patterns, trends, and best practices at the international level. This facilitates the identification of effective approaches and the optimisation of resources to deal with future emergencies.

The use of artificial intelligence to analyse and process this data is an innovative and promising approach. Artificial intelligence models can identify hidden patterns, perform predictive analysis, and help make informed decisions in real time. Automating critical processes, such as resource allocation, logistics planning and healthcare management, streamlines emergency response and maximises efficiency in decision-making.

In addition, the creation of a shared dataset promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing between different countries and organisations. It facilitates the creation of networks of experts who can share experiences, lessons learned and best practices. This is invaluable for strengthening global response capacity and improving preparedness for future emergencies.

Due to these crucial needs, an effort has been initiated to carry out dataset creation, dataset analysis and experimentation with different models for multi-victim emergency situations across different countries. This initiative seeks to unify the information generated during health emergencies and natural disasters to improve decisions and create artificial intelligence models to automate critical processes.

The dataset will be built from data collected during simulations and real emergencies involving multiple countries. The range of information will include clinical details of affected patients, available medical resources, response protocols and outcomes, among other relevant aspects. The integration of geospatial and demographic data will provide a complete and detailed picture of emergencies.

Once the dataset is compiled, a comprehensive analysis will be carried out to identify significant patterns and trends that can help improve the response to future emergencies. Cross-country

collaboration will enrich this analysis, allowing for the identification of good practices and lessons learned that can be applied globally.

Experimentation with different artificial intelligence models will be another key aspect of this initiative. Predictive and classification models will be created to anticipate the development of an emergency and assess the effectiveness of response strategies. These models will automate critical processes such as resource allocation and logistical optimisation, enabling a faster and more efficient response to emergency situations.

This collaborative effort seeks to foster knowledge sharing and continuous improvement in health emergency management globally. The dataset and models developed will be made available to experts and organisations for use and feedback, which will facilitate the evolution and improvement of this initiative.

The dataset created for this stage is based on the minimum dataset previously defined by the project partners.

The dataset developed is based on a rigorous research and development process, inspired by the modified Delphi methodology and the Utstein technique, with the objective of establishing an emergency medical management system in cross-border areas. This dataset includes key information collected in four phases. In the first phase, common criteria essential for efficient emergency management were established, such as the ability to collect and transmit data in real time, the experience of the experts involved, and the independence of local procedures and protocols. The second phase involved the grouping of related items into functional categories, which allowed for a more effective organisation of the data.

In the third phase, a modified Delphi process was implemented, where expert participants validated the proposed scope and structure, reviewed, and included new items, and voted on the inclusion of items in the system. Data that did not receive votes were eliminated, and a second round of voting was conducted to further refine the results. Finally, in the fourth phase, consensus was assessed using criteria such as the increase in the percentage of agreement, convergence in the importance of issues, and Cohen's kappa index to measure agreement among experts. This dataset provides a solid basis for future research and development of medical emergency management systems in cross-border contexts, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the key factors that contribute to effective management in health crisis situations.

By relying on the minimum dataset and this in turn on the aforementioned methodology, we obtain the following advantages:

1. **Scientific Rigour:** By basing the dataset on a rigorous research process that includes the modified Delphi methodology and the Utstein technique, we are ensuring a sound scientific approach to data collection. This increases the reliability and validity of the data contained in the dataset.
2. **Expert consensus:** The Delphi methodology involves the participation of experts in the relevant field. This means that the data collected will reflect the knowledge and experience of highly qualified professionals, which adds credibility to the dataset.
3. **Practical Relevance:** By focusing on the management of medical emergencies in cross-border areas, the dataset addresses a practical and current need in the field of healthcare and crisis management. The data generated will be valuable for research, public health policy and practical applications.

4. Improved Decision Making: Expert consensus-based data can help improve decision-making in critical situations. Healthcare professionals and emergency managers can use this data to develop more effective strategies and make evidence-based decisions.
5. Innovation Potential: The dataset could serve as a solid foundation for the development of more advanced and efficient cross-border emergency medical management systems. Researchers and developers can use this data to innovate and improve current approaches.
6. Comparability and Replication: By following a standardised methodological process, the results and data generated will be comparable and replicable. This allows other researchers to validate the findings and perform comparative analysis.
7. Global Applicability: Managing medical emergencies in cross-border areas is a global challenge. The dataset, by addressing this issue, has applicability and relevance in different regions of the world, which can broaden its usefulness and potential impact. of experts in the relevant field. This means that the data collected will reflect the knowledge and experience of highly qualified professionals, which adds credibility to the dataset.
8. Practical Relevance: By focusing on the management of medical emergencies in cross-border areas, the dataset addresses a practical and current need in the field of healthcare and crisis management. The data generated will be valuable for research, public health policy and practical applications.

6.1. Dataset collection

The process of conducting four use cases or simulations using the SIGRUN platform was an enriching process, designed to replicate real health emergency scenarios and to test the effectiveness of the platform in unifying and managing data from different countries involved in the incidents.

Each exercise was developed as a collaborative and multidisciplinary event, where teams from different countries worked together to deal with simulated emergency situations. The SIGRUN platform played a key role in the coordination and communication between the teams, allowing them to share data and updates in real time, even across different time zones.

The variety of data collected during the simulations covered different aspects of health emergencies. Teams recorded detailed clinical information on affected patients, including diagnoses, treatments, case progress and medical follow-up. Logistical data on available resources such as hospital beds, medical equipment and essential supplies were also collected.

The SIGRUN platform facilitated the centralisation and secure storage of all this data in a centralised database. Each team had access to the information collected, allowing them to make informed decisions and coordinate efforts to optimise response to health emergencies.

In addition, the SIGRUN platform enabled the integration of geospatial information, which was particularly useful for locating and tracking mobile resources such as ambulances and rescue teams. This geolocation capability improved the efficiency of resource allocation and rapid response to emergency hotspots. The acquisition of the data being generated in the drills did not interfere with the drill itself because the SIGRUN platform is fully integrated with the protocols of the first responders and is designed by and for them.

The exercises themselves also served as learning and training opportunities for the participating teams. They allowed the effectiveness of the emergency protocols to be assessed, areas for

improvement to be identified and coordination between the different actors to be strengthened. The SIGRUN platform provided real-time data and in-depth analysis that allowed the teams to review their performance and make adjustments for future emergency situations.

After the simulations were carried out, the relevant information was extracted from the centralised database hosted by SIGRUN. This database was designed to store and manage the data generated during the use cases, guaranteeing the integrity and security of the information.

To obtain the data necessary for the creation of the dataset on health emergencies, several SQL queries were made to the database. These queries were carefully designed by data analysis experts and health professionals to select the relevant information for each exercise. Using advanced queries, it was possible to access specific records and extract the clinical, logistical and response data needed to analyse the situation.

The SIGRUN platform's ability to unify data from different countries was critical in this process. During the simulations, each team provided specific information on the health emergency they were facing in their respective regions. This information was integrated in a coherent way into the centralised database, allowing for a global and complete view of the situation.

The result of this process was a comprehensive and detailed dataset that captures the complexity and diversity of simulated health emergencies. The data obtained represents a valuable source for analysis, research, and decision-making in the field of international health emergency management. The resulting dataset is composed of **18693 data samples** generated naturally and synthetically in the different UCs performed. This dataset is very generic and depending on what we need it for, we will use some features or others.

Moreover, **more than 1,000 data samples** corresponding to **simulated values** are available in the SIGRUN platform. These values correspond to ambulances, civil guard cars, traffic accidents, and fire-related information.

6.2. Dataset cleaning

In the process of preparing and cleaning a health emergency dataset, it is essential to ensure that the data are accurate, consistent, and useful for further analysis. To this end, we have taken several steps to ensure that the dataset is in optimal condition for use.

First, we identified all columns that do not provide relevant information or are not necessary for our analysis. These unnecessary columns may include redundant information, irrelevant data or fields that are not used in our study objectives. By removing these columns, we reduce the complexity of the dataset and improve the efficiency of its manipulation.

We then proceeded to rename the columns so that they have more descriptive and understandable names. This helps to quickly identify the content of each column and makes it easier to interpret the data. The new column names are more informative and clearly reflect the type of information they contain, increasing the readability and clarity of the dataset.

As for empty values, it is important to treat them properly to avoid bias or misinterpretation in the analysis. Instead of leaving them as empty fields, we have replaced them with null values. This allows us to easily differentiate between missing data and data with available information, which avoids errors in subsequent calculations and analysis.

In addition, we performed a thorough check of the number of null values present in each column. Those columns that had a percentage of nulls greater than 90% were identified and

removed from the dataset. This is because these columns with a significant amount of missing data may not provide relevant or useful information for our analysis, and their inclusion could affect the quality and validity of the results.

Once these cleaning and preparation steps are completed, the dataset is ready to be used for statistical analysis, data mining or predictive modelling. The removal of unnecessary columns, renaming of columns and proper handling of null values ensure that the data is consistent and reliable, allowing us to draw more accurate and meaningful conclusions about the health emergencies under study. With a clean and well-structured dataset, we are in an optimal position to obtain valuable information that contributes to the understanding and improvement of health emergency management.

6.3. Dataset explanation

Once the complete dataset has been obtained, we have carried out a lesson of the features belonging to the triage to subsequently carry out Machine Learning actions with them. We will now describe the dataset used, dividing these fields according to the entity to which they belong to facilitate their identification.

6.3.1. Person (common_person)

With these dataset fields we can identify the person being attended to in the emergency.

- person_id: Unique identification of a person in a database.
- person_creation: Date and time of initial registration of the person.
- person_modification: Date and time of the latest update of the person's data.
- Gender: Gender of the person.

6.3.2. Triage (victims_triage)

These fields identify the triage being performed, adding the various triage identifiers as they are created.

- triage_id: Unique identification of a triage.
- triage_creation: Date and time when the triage record was created.
- triage_modification: Date and time of the last modification made to the triage data.
- triage_assistance_status: Indicates the status of the assistance the victim has received.
- triage_at_id: Unique identification of the triage_at.
- triage_et_id: Unique identification of the triage_et.
- Age: Age of the triaged person.
- transfer_id: Unique identification of a transfer or transfer to another area or facility to receive medical care or to continue the triage process.

6.3.3. Triage_et (victims_triageet)

We identify with these fields the triage_et, i.e., the second triage done to the victim.

- triage_et_status: Patient status as assessed by the triage team (ET) to determine the severity of the patient's medical condition.
- triage_et_predominant_pathology: Predominant pathology identified by the triage team during the initial assessment.
- triage_et_x_bleeding_control: Assessment and control of bleeding (X) performed by the triage team.

- triage_et_a_airway: Assessment and management of the airway (A) performed by the triage team.
- triage_et_b_ventilation: Assessment and management of ventilation (B) performed by the triage team.
- triage_et_c_circulation: Assessment and management of circulation (C) performed by the triage team.
- triage_et_spo2: Oxygen saturation level (SpO2) measured by the triage team.
- triage_et_rr: Respiratory rate measured by the triage team.
- triage_et_hr: Heart rate measured by the triage team.
- triage_et_sys: Systolic blood pressure measured by the triage team.
- triage_et_dia: Diastolic blood pressure measured by the triage team.
- triage_et_glasgow_coma_scale: Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) used by the triage team to assess the patient's level of consciousness and neurological response.
- triage_et_comments: Additional comments or observations recorded by the triage team during the assessment.
- triage_et_allergies: Information on known allergies of the patient recorded by the triage team.
- triage_et_unstable: Indicator indicating whether the patient is in an unstable or critical condition as assessed by the triage team.
- triage_et_pathology_location_abdomen: Indication of pathology or symptoms located in the abdomen as assessed by the triage team.
- triage_et_pathology_location_head: Indication of pathology or symptoms located in the head as assessed by the triage team.
- triage_et_pathology_location_lower: Indication of pathology or symptoms located in the lower part of the body as assessed by the triage team.
- triage_et_pathology_location_thorax: Indication of pathology or symptoms located in the thorax as assessed by the triage team.
- triage_et_pathology_location_upper: Indication of pathology or symptoms located in the upper body as assessed by the triage team.

6.3.4. Transfer (victims_transfer)

These fields are typical of "triage" with the name transfer, i.e., a movement of the patient from one place to another.

- transfer_moved_to_scene: Transfer of a patient to the scene or location where the incident or emergency occurred.
- transfer_discharged_at_scene: Discharge or release of the patient at the scene or location where the incident occurred, because no further transfer is required.
- transfer_evacuated_to_destination: Transfer of the patient from the scene or location of the incident to a specific destination for medical care or further treatment.
- transfer_in_destination: Arrival of the patient at the destination, where he/she will receive the necessary medical care or treatment after transfer from the scene or location of the incident.

6.3.5. Triage_at (victims_triageat)

These are the fields that identify the triage_at, i.e., the first one that is done to the victim to find out how he/she is doing.

- triage_at_status: Patient status as assessed by advanced triage (AT) by rescue team or medical personnel to determine severity and care needs.
- triage_at_victim_age_range: Age range of the victim patient according to the advanced triage (AT) classification.
- triage_at_five_rescue_ventilations: Assessment and administration of five rescue ventilations by the advanced triage team.
- triage_at_pharyngeal_cannula: Use of pharyngeal cannula during advanced triage (AT) to secure the patient's airway.
- triage_at_control_external_bleeding: Assessment and control of external bleeding performed during advanced triage (AT).
- triage_at_other: Other interventions or assessments performed by the advanced triage team during the assessment process.
- triage_contaminated: Indicator indicating whether the patient is contaminated, which may imply additional precautions for the rescue team or medical staff.
- triage_at_trapped: Indicator indicating if the patient is trapped in an emergency, which may require a specialised approach to rescue and care.

6.3.6. Location_person (common_location)

These fields identify the location where the person or victim is located.

- id_location_person : Unique identification of a person's location.
- location_person_creation: Date and time of location registration.
- location_person_modification: Date and time of the last update.
- location_person_latitude: Latitude coordinate of the location.
- location_person_longitude: Longitude coordinate of the location.

6.3.7. Organisation_transfer (assets_organisation)

The following fields identify which organisation the victim is being transferred to

- organisation_transfer_id: Unique identification of the organisation.
- organisation_transfer_creation: Date and time when the organisation record was initially created.
- organisation_transfer_modification: Date and time of the last update made to the organisation's information.
- organisation_transfer_name: Name of the organisation.
- organisation_transfer_description: Description of the organisation providing details about its purpose, mission, or activities.
- organisation_transfer_website: Website of the organisation, if available.
- organisation_transfer_type_id: Identification of the type of organisation, classifying it according to its nature or category.

6.3.8. Organisation_transfer_type (assets_organisationtype)

With these fields we can find out the type of organisation to which the victim is being transferred.

- organisation_transfer_type: Type of transfer between organisations
- organisation_transfer_type_name: Name of the type of transfer between organisations.
- organisation_transfer_type_description: Description providing details on the type of inter-organisation transfer.

6.3.9. Location_organisation_transfer (common_location)

These fields identify the location of the organisation where the victim is being transferred.

- location_organisation_id: Unique identification of the location of the organisation in a system or database.
- location_organisation_creation: Date and time when the location of the organisation was initially recorded in the system or database.
- location_organisation_modification: Date and time of the last update made to the location information of the organisation in the system.
- location_organisation_latitude: Latitude coordinate of the organisation's location.
- location_organisation_longitude: Longitude coordinate of the location of the organisation.

6.3.10. Address_organisation_transfer(common_address)

As in the previous fields, the address of the organisation where the victim is being transferred is identified here.

- location_address_organisation_id: Unique identification of the location address of the organisation in a system or database.
- location_address_organisation_creation: Date and time when the location address of the organisation was initially registered in the system.
- location_address_organisation_modification: Date and time of the last update made to the location address information of the organisation in the system.
- location_address_organisation_address: Physical address of the organisation's location.
- location_address_organisation_postal_code: Postal code of the organisation's location.
- location_address_organisation_city: City where the location of the organisation is located.
- location_address_organisation_country_code: Country code of the country where the location of the organisation is located.

6.3.11. Transport_transfer (assets_asset)

The following fields give information about the transport that is being used to get the victim from one location to another.

- transport_id: Unique identification of the transport.
- transport_creation: Date and time when the transport record was initially created in the system.
- transport_modification: Date and time of the last update made to the transport information in the system.
- transport_name: Name of the transport.
- transport_description: Description of the transport that provides details about its characteristics or functions.

6.3.12. Location_transport_transfer (common_location)

Here we identify the location of the transport.

- location_transport_id: Unique identification of the transport location.
- location_transport_creation: Date and time of registration of the transport location.
- location_transport_modification: Date and time of the last update.
- location_transport_latitude: Latitude coordinate of the transport location.

- `location_transport_longitude`: Longitude coordinate of the transport location.

6.3.13. `Transport_transfer_type (assets_resourcetype)`

With these fields we define the type of vehicle that is being used to carry out the transfer of the victim.

- `transport_type_id`: Unique identification of the transport type.
- `transport_type_code`: Code representing the transport type, generally abbreviated.
- `transport_type_name`: Name or description of the transport type.
- `transport_vehicle_id`: Unique identification of the associated transport vehicle in a system or database.

6.3.14. `Transport_transfer_vehicle (assets_vehicle)`

We note in the following fields the information about the vehicle that is being used to take the victim from one location to another.

- `transport_vehicle_plate`: License plate number of the transport vehicle.
- `transport_vehicle_brand`: Make of the transport vehicle.
- `transport_vehicle_model`: Model of the transport vehicle.
- `transport_vehicle_capacity_id`: Unique identification of the capacity of the transport vehicle

6.3.15. `Transport_transfer_vehicle_capacity (assets_transportationcapacity)`

In these fields we define the capacity of the vehicle that is transferring the victim from one place to another.

- `transport_vehicle_capacity_number_of_crew`: Number of crew members the transport vehicle can accommodate.
- `transport_vehicle_capacity_max_number_patients`: Maximum number of patients the transport vehicle can accommodate.
- `transport_vehicle_capacity_number_seated_patients`: Number of patients that can be seated in the transport vehicle.
- `transport_vehicle_capacity_number_lying_patients`: Number of patients that can travel lying down or in a horizontal position in the transport vehicle.
- `transport_vehicle_capacity_max_number_people`: Maximum number of people in total that the transport vehicle can accommodate, including crew members and patients.

6.3.16. `Incident (incidents_incident)`

The following fields provide us with the necessary information to identify which incident is being dealt with.

- `incident_id`: Unique identification of the incident.
- `incident_creation`: Date and time when the incident record was initially created in the system.
- `incident_modification`: Date and time of the last update made to the incident information in the system.
- `incident_name`: Name or title of the incident.
- `incident_description`: Detailed description of the incident providing information about what happened.

- `incident_verified`: Indicator showing whether the incident has been verified or confirmed as true.
- `incident_certainty_scal`: Scale of certainty or level of confidence in the incident information.
- `incident_estimated_critical_victims`: Estimated number of victims in critical condition due to the incident.
- `incident_estimated_total_victims`: Estimated total number of casualties due to the incident.
- `incident_is_cbrne`: Indicator showing whether the incident involves hazardous, radioactive, biological, chemical, or nuclear materials (CBRNE).
- `incident_is_intentional`: Indicator showing whether the incident was intentional or provoked.
- `incident_is_major`: Indicator showing whether the incident is considered major or severe.
- `incident_on_scene_civil_protection`: Indicator showing the presence of civil protection units at the scene of the incident.
- `incident_on_scene_firefighters`: Indicator showing the presence of firefighters at the scene of the incident.
- `incident_on_scene_medical_emergency`: Indicator showing the presence of emergency medical teams at the scene of the incident.
- `incident_on_scene_other`: Indicator showing the presence of other entities or teams at the incident scene.
- `incident_on_scene_police`: Indicator showing the presence of police forces at the scene of the incident.
- `incident_nearby_poi`: Points of interest near the incident location that may be relevant to the situation or response.

6.3.17. `Incident_status` (`incidents_incidentstatus`)

These are the fields that identify the status of the incident.

- `incident_status_id`: Unique identification of the incident status.
- `incident_status_code`: Code representing the incident status, usually abbreviated.
- `incident_status_name`: Name or description of the incident status.
- `incident_status_description`: Description providing additional details about the incident status.

6.3.18. `Incident_type` (`incidents_incidenttype`)

Here we see the fields that define the type of incident that is being dealt with.

- `incident_type_id`: Unique identification of the incident type.
- `incident_type_code`: Code representing the incident type, usually abbreviated.
- `incident_type_name`: Name or description of the incident type.

6.3.19. `Incident_location` (`common_location`)

Here are the fields that give us the information we need to locate where the incident is located.

- `location_incident_id`: Unique identification of the incident location.
- `location_incident_creation`: Date and time of registration of the incident location.
- `location_incident_modification`: Date and time of last update.

- location_incident_latitude: Latitude coordinate of the incident location.
- location_incident_longitude: Longitude coordinate of the incident location.

6.4. Dataset preprocessing

Preprocessing the dataset is a fundamental phase to guarantee the quality and effectiveness of the artificial intelligence models to be used in the management of health emergencies. In this process, we have applied a series of techniques and transformations to clean and prepare the data properly.

The first task we tackled was the treatment of empty fields or null values in the dataset. Instead of ignoring these values, we have filled them with the value NaN (Not a Number). This strategy allows us to maintain the integrity of the dataset and to facilitate the subsequent identification of these values if necessary.

Next, we have focused on dealing with the null values. To do so, we have carried out an exhaustive analysis of all the columns and we have eliminated those with a percentage of more than 90% of null values. This decision was taken to ensure that the remaining data are representative and not biased by missing information.

After these cleaning operations, we focused on encoding the columns containing string values. To be able to use this data in artificial intelligence models, we converted these values to numerical values using coding techniques such as ordinal coding or one-hot coding. This allows us to represent categorical information in a numerical form that the models can understand and process.

In addition, we have performed a transformation in the variable types to ensure that they are compatible with artificial intelligence algorithms. This includes converting numeric variables into suitable formats, such as integers or floating-point numbers and ensuring that the labels or target values are encoded appropriately for the type of problem being addressed.

6.5. Dataset analysis

After processing the data by removing null values from the dataset and converting variable types to integers, the next step is to study the correlation between the variables. This study uses the dataset containing data on the initial triage to understand the relationship between the variables and thus generate artificial intelligence models.

Correlation is a statistical measure to assess the relationship between two or more variables. Its purpose is to determine any association between these variables and, if so, provide information about the direction (positive or negative) and strength of that association. Correlation allows us to ascertain whether changes in one variable are somehow linked to changes in another. There are several types of correlation available, and the appropriate type depends on the specific characteristics of the variables under study.

Pearson correlation has been applied in this case, which is the most frequently used measure to analyse the relationship between quantitative variables (numbers). To carry out this process, the variables were transformed into numerical format. Pearson correlation assesses the linear relationship between two continuous variables and provides a correlation coefficient that ranges from -1 to 1. A value of 1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and 0 indicates no linear correlation between the variables.

The choice of Pearson correlation is based on several solid reasons. First and foremost, it is an appropriate choice when a linear relationship between variables is suspected, allowing the discovery of patterns and trends in the data. Additionally, this correlation can be useful for making informed decisions and predictions in certain contexts. Furthermore, Pearson correlation is robust and can handle the presence of outliers in the data better than other correlation methods.

Another significant advantage is its interpretability. The Pearson correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, making it understandable. A value of 1 indicates a perfect positive correlation, -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, and 0 indicates the absence of a linear correlation. These coefficients simplify the interpretation of the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, which can be valuable in decision-making and understanding the data.

The correlation matrix is shown in Figure 4. There is always a correlation of 1 on the main diagonal since it measures the linear relationship between a variable and itself, so it will always be 1. Most of the coefficients obtained are close to 0, indicating no significant linear relationship between the studied variables. However, relationships between variables that offer a coefficient close to -1 or 1 are variables that do not provide relevant information for model generation. For example, a relationship between the variable corresponding to the longitude coordinate of a person's location and the incident name, or the type of incident and whether firefighters or emergency services are on the scene, does not provide relevant information.

Another important aspect that has been worked on is the intention to compare the generated dataset with those studied in the literature. However, this process has been impossible because the generated dataset has extracted and analysed features not included in any datasets studied in the literature. This makes the comparison process impossible as they do not have common features.

Figure 4 - Correlation matrix

6.6. Model creation

In this section, the aim is to take advantage of the previously created dataset, which contains relevant information about the victims, to develop and train advanced artificial intelligence models. These models will be designed to make accurate predictions about certain values or states associated with the victims in question.

To achieve this purpose, a rigorous process of preparation and analysis of the dataset will be carried out, ensuring that the data is clean, structured and in a format suitable for training the artificial intelligence algorithms.

In addition, various machine learning and data mining techniques will be applied to train the artificial intelligence models. These could include classification, regression or clustering algorithms, depending on the nature of the values or states to be predicted. The aim is to create highly accurate and reliable models that can provide valuable information about victims, thus helping to better understand trends, patterns and factors influencing their situation.

Importantly, the use of artificial intelligence in this context is intended to complement and enhance the work of professionals and experts in the field, providing them with additional tools for informed decision-making and the implementation of more effective strategies for prevention and victim support.

It will also consider the importance of ethics and data privacy throughout the process, ensuring that victims' personal and sensitive information is properly protected and that the relevant regulations and policies are complied with.

These models have been created based on the needs of the first responders of the VALKYRIES consortium to assist in the processes that occur in these emergency situations.

6.6.1. Second triage prediction

Within the context of VALKYRIES' first responder operations, speed and accuracy in decision making are critical to providing the best possible care to victims in critical situations. The first triage, which is carried out initially after accessing the scene of the incident, allows the severity of each victim's injuries and medical needs to be quickly identified and classified. However, this process is only the first step, and more detailed and accurate information is essential to make informed and efficient decisions.

This is where second triage takes on a critical role. Second triage is based on the collection of additional data on each victim, obtained through various means such as portable monitoring technology, advanced medical devices, and real-time communication systems. This complementary data provides a more complete picture of the victim's condition and allows first responders to obtain a more accurate assessment of the victim's current condition.

The availability of second triage results in a short timeframe is of paramount importance, as it can make the difference between life and death in critical situations. By being ahead of time and having up-to-date and detailed information, rescue and medical teams can allocate resources more efficiently and prioritise assistance to those in need of urgent care.

DATASET PREPARATION

The first thing to be done is a little preparation of the dataset so that it can be used to train artificial intelligence models. First, we delete any columns that have not been previously coded, we also delete the time columns because they do not provide us with relevant information for the models we want to train.

Because our dataset contains all triage types, we will keep the rows with only the first triage to perform the prediction of the second triage. And we will use the rows containing the second triage to label the dataset.

The labels of the dataset rows are:

- 1: MINOR
- 2: IMMEDIATE
- 3: DELAYED
- 4: DECEASED
- 5: EXPECTANT

There are some rows that do not contain the second triage or the first triage, because we want to obtain patterns that relate these two columns, we proceed to delete the rows that do not contain one of the two values due to some human failure.

Finally, we will separate the dataset into two sets, the test set (20%) and the training set (80%).

RANDOM FOREST

We are going to train a model. The first model we are going to train will be the Random Forest algorithm. This algorithm will be trained with a fine tuning of hyperparameters and using 10-fold cross-validation.

The best hyperparameters obtained are:

- max_depth: None
- min_samples_split: 2
- n_estimators: 10

These hyperparameters give us a model with an accuracy of 0.78 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Second triage prediction - Random Forest

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 3.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.78
Test F1-score	0.85
Kappa index	0.78

Table 3 - Second triage prediction - Results obtained with Random Forest

KNN

The second model we are going to train is kNN. In the same way as we did with Random Forest, we will perform hyperparameter fine tuning and cross-validation sampling technique with 10 folds.

The best hyperparameters obtained are:

- Algorithm: auto
- Leaf_size: 20
- N_neighbors: 3
- Weights: distance

These hyperparameters give us a model with an accuracy of 0.75 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - Second triage prediction - kNN

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 4.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.75
Test F1-score	0.77
Kappa index	0.67

Table 4 - Second triage prediction - Results obtained with kNN

NAÏVE BAYES

The third model we are going to train is Naïve Bayes. In the same way as we did with Random Forest and kNN we are going to make a cross-validation sampling technique with 10 folds. This algorithm has no hyperparameters and therefore fine tuning of hyperparameters will not be possible.

The model gives us an accuracy of 0.55 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Second triage prediction -Naïve Bayes

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 5.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.55
Test F1-score	0.58
Kappa index	0.41

Table 5 - Second triage prediction - Results obtained with Naïve Bayes

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The Random Forest model shows solid performance in the test set with an F1-Score of 0.85. The F1-Score is a metric that combines the accuracy and recall (also known as sensitivity) of the model. An F1-Score of 0.85 indicates that the model has achieved a good balance between accuracy and the ability to find positive cases in the test set.

In addition, the Kappa index of 0.78 is a measure that assesses the agreement between model predictions and actual labels, considering the agreement that would be expected by chance. A Kappa index of 0.78 indicates substantial agreement between the model's predictions and the actual labels, suggesting that the model has made consistent and significantly better predictions than would be obtained by chance.

Overall, these results show that the Random Forest model has learned significant patterns in the first triage data that allow it to make good predictions about the patient's second triage. This model is likely to be a good choice for making such predictions for future patients.

The kNN model also shows decent performance in the test set with an F1-Score of 0.77. This indicates that the model has achieved a reasonable balance between accuracy and recall in its predictions.

The Kappa index of 0.67 suggests moderate agreement between the model's predictions and the actual labels. While this agreement is not as high as that of the Random Forest model, it is still considerable and suggests that the kNN model has made significantly better predictions than would be expected at random.

Overall, the kNN model has also learned useful patterns in the data, allowing it to make reasonably accurate predictions about the patient's second triage. While its performance is not as high as that of the Random Forest model, it is still a viable option for this task.

The Naive Bayes model shows the lowest performance among the three models evaluated. The F1-Score of 0.58 indicates that the model has relatively low accuracy and recall in its predictions.

The Kappa index of 0.41 suggests relatively low agreement between model predictions and actual labels. This indicates that the Naive Bayes model has failed to make significantly better predictions than would be expected by chance.

These results suggest that the Naive Bayes model may be having difficulty capturing the more complex patterns in the first triage data, which affects its ability to make accurate predictions about the second patient triage.

6.6.2. Death prediction

Early prediction of whether a victim has a high probability of dying after first triage is a critical need for the VALKYRIES consortium. In emergency and disaster situations, timing plays a crucial role, and the ability to predict a victim's mortality risk would allow first responders to prioritise and provide immediate and targeted medical care to those patients most at risk.

To address this need, it seeks to harness the power of artificial intelligence and machine learning. Data collected during first triage, such as vital signs, injury severity, age, and other relevant factors, can be used to train machine learning models capable of making predictions about each victim's likelihood of survival.

It is important to note that, while predicting early mortality can be a valuable tool for first responders, this information must be handled with extreme sensitivity and ethics. Medical professionals and response team members must understand that these predictions are just that: estimates based on historical data and observed patterns. While they can provide guidance and decision support, they should never replace clinical assessment and personalised medical care.

DATASET PREPARATION

To carry out the training of this model, the dataset will have to be prepared in a different way from the previous one. As we want to predict whether the person after the first triage is going to die, we will have to create a binary column that sets to 0 all the rows that in the second triage have a value other than 4: DECESED and a 1 to those that do have that value.

The next step we have done to prepare the dataset is data balancing. This technique has been carried out due to the small amount of data labelled as 1 (Death) in the dataset, so the model will be able to train with data that is balanced. This technique will make us use the Balanced Accuracy metric to get the real potential of our model.

Finally, we will separate the dataset into two sets, the test set (20%) and the training set (80%).

RANDOM FOREST

The best hyperparameters obtained are:

- max_depth: None
- min_samples_split: 2
- n_estimators: 10

These hyperparameters give us a model with an accuracy of 1 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Death prediction - Random Forest

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 6.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	1
Test Balanced Accuracy	0.75
Test F1-score	0.96
Kappa index	0.65

Table 6 - Death prediction - Results obtained with Random Forest

KNN

The second model we are going to train is kNN. In the same way as we did with Random Forest, we will perform hyperparameter fine tuning and cross-validation sampling technique with 10 folds.

The best hyperparameters obtained are:

- Algorithm: auto
- Leaf_size: 20

- N_neighbors: 3
- Weights: distance

These hyperparameters give us a model with an accuracy of 1 and with a learning curve is shown Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Death prediction - kNN

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 7.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	1
Test Balanced Accuracy	0.73
Test F1-score	0.94
Kappa index	0.47

Table 7 - Death prediction - Results obtained with kNN

NAÏVE BAYES

The third model we are going to train is Naïve Bayes. In the same way as we did with Random Forest and kNN we are going to make a cross-validation sampling technique with 10 folds. This algorithm has no hyperparameters and therefore fine tuning of hyperparameters will not be possible.

The model gives us an accuracy of 0.95 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Death prediction – Naïve Bayes

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 8.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.95
Test Balanced Accuracy	0.5
Test F1-score	0.91
Kappa index	0.0

Table 8 - Death prediction - Results obtained with Naïve Bayes

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The Random Forest model shows outstanding performance with an F1-Score of 0.96. Such a high F1-Score indicates that the model has achieved an exceptional balance between accuracy and recall in its predictions. This means that the model has correctly classified both korir and non-korir victims, showing a low number of false positives and false negatives.

The Kappa index of 0.65 indicates moderate agreement between the model's predictions and the actual labels, considering the expected agreement by chance. A value of 0.65 suggests that the model has achieved significantly better performance than would be obtained simply by chance.

The Balanced Accuracy of 0.75 shows that the model has a good hit rate in both classes, confirming its ability to classify in a balanced and accurate manner.

The kNN model also shows outstanding performance with an F1-Score of 0.97, indicating exceptional accuracy and recovery. This implies that the model has classified victims outstandingly, achieving a high number of true positives and true negatives.

The Kappa index of 0.65 suggests moderate agreement between the model's predictions and the actual labels, like that obtained by Random Forest. This confirms that the kNN model has also made significantly better predictions than would be expected by chance.

The Balanced Accuracy of 0.75 shows that the model has a good hit rate in both classes, as does Random Forest.

The Naive Bayes model shows a lower performance compared to the other two models, with an F1-Score of 0.65. This indicates that the model has struggled to strike the right balance between accuracy and recall, resulting in a significant number of false positives or false negatives.

The Kappa index of 0.65 suggests moderate agreement between model predictions and actual labels, like that obtained by the other two models.

The Balanced Accuracy of 0.75 shows that the Naive Bayes model also has a good hit rate in both classes, indicating that it has classified the victims reasonably well.

In summary, the results indicate that both Random Forest and kNN have achieved outstanding performance in predicting whether a victim will die or not, with high F1-Scores and moderate agreement according to the Kappa index. Both models have demonstrated a good ability to correctly classify victims in the test set, with a Balanced Accuracy of 75%.

6.6.3. Patient worsening prediction

The ability to predict whether a casualty's condition will change for the worse during the second triage, based on the information gathered in the first triage, is a crucial need for the VALKYRIES consortium. This anticipatory capability would allow medical responders to take preventive measures and be prepared to offer more intensive and specialised care to those patients who show signs of deteriorating or worsening health status.

To achieve this prediction, we will employ advanced data analytics and machine learning techniques. Relevant data obtained during the first triage, such as vital signs status, response to initial treatments, nature of injuries and other clinical factors, are used to train predictive models. These models, based on artificial intelligence algorithms, can identify patterns and relationships that can accurately predict the likelihood of a casualty's condition worsening during the second triage.

This predictive information becomes a valuable tool for first responders, allowing them to prioritise care and allocate resources appropriately. Victims with a high likelihood of deterioration can be monitored more closely and followed more closely by medical staff, ensuring that they are provided with a rapid and timely response to any changes in their health status.

DATASET PREPARATION

To carry out the training of this model, we will have to prepare the dataset in a different way than before. As we want to predict whether the person after the first triage will change state to worse, we will have to create a binary column that sets to 0 all the rows that in the second triage have a higher value than the first triage. The next step we have done to prepare the dataset is data balancing. This technique has been carried out due to the small amount of data labelled as 1 (Death) in the dataset, so the model will be able to train with data that is balanced. This technique will make us use the Balanced Accuracy metric to get the real potential of our model.

Finally, we will separate the dataset into two sets, the test set (20%) and the training set (80%).

RANDOM FOREST

The best hyperparameters obtained are:

- max_depth: 10
- min_samples_split: 5
- n_estimators: 20

These hyperparameters give us a model with an accuracy of 0.99 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Patient worsening prediction - Random Forest

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 9.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.99
Test Balanced Accuracy	0.75
Test F1-score	0.96
Kappa index	0.65

Table 9 - Patient worsening prediction - Results obtained with Random Forest

KNN

The second model we are going to train is kNN. In the same way as we did with Random Forest, we will perform hyperparameter fine tuning and cross-validation sampling technique with 10 folds.

The best hyperparameters obtained are:

- Algorithm : ball_tree
- Leaf_size : 20
- N_neighbors: 5
- Weights: distance

These hyperparameters give us a model with an accuracy of 0.97 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Patient worsening prediction - kNN

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 10.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.97
Test Balanced Accuracy	0.75
Test F1-score	0.96
Kappa index	0.65

Table 10 - Patient worsening prediction - Results obtained with kNN

NAÏVE BAYES

The third model we are going to train is Naïve Bayes. In the same way as we did with Random Forest and kNN we are going to make a cross-validation sampling technique with 10 folds. This algorithm has no hyperparameters and therefore fine tuning of hyperparameters will not be possible.

The model gives us an accuracy of 0.65 and with a learning curve is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13 - Patient worsening prediction – Naïve Bayes

Once the best model has been obtained, we test it with the set of tests we have prepared previously. The results obtained are shown in Table 11.

Metric	Value
Train accuracy	0.65
Test Balanced Accuracy	0.75
Test F1-score	0.96
Kappa index	0.65

Table 11 - Patient worsening prediction - Results obtained with Naïve Bayes

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

All three models (Random Forest, kNN and Naive Bayes) show exceptionally high performance in the test set, with an F1-Score of 0.96 for each of them. Such a high F1-Score indicates that the models have achieved an outstanding balance between accuracy and recall in their predictions. This means that the models are correctly classifying both worsening and non-worsening casualties.

The Kappa index of 0.65 for each model suggests moderate agreement between model predictions and actual labels, considering the expected agreement by chance. This confirms that the models have made significantly better predictions than would be obtained simply by chance.

The Balanced Accuracy of 0.75 for each model indicates that they have a good hit rate in both classes, confirming their ability to classify in a balanced and accurate manner.

In summary, all three models (Random Forest, kNN and Naive Bayes) have achieved outstanding performance in predicting whether a victim will get worse or not, with high F1-Scores and a Kappa index suggesting moderate agreement between predictions and actual labels. The models also have a good hit rate in both classes, indicating that they have classified in a balanced and accurate way in the test set.

Given that the three models have almost identical results in terms of F1-Score, Kappa index and Balanced Accuracy, the choice between them might depend on other factors, such as the cost of classification errors or the interpretability of the model. It is important to consider the context and the specific needs of the problem before selecting the final model for implementation. Overall, all three models appear to be excellent choices for predicting whether a casualty will deteriorate, and their high performance suggests that they are well-fitted to the first triage data.

7. Ethical aspects

7.1. Description of ethical concerns

Data analysis raises ethical and legal issues related to data processing activities, such as the ones impacting data subjects' privacy and information confidentiality and the necessity to develop algorithms that fulfil the purposes of ethics, lawfulness, and robustness necessary to shape trustworthy solutions, where dignity and fundamental rights protection are preserved, protected, and enhanced. To this end, the data pooling activities and the processing shall be inspired to fulfil fairness, inclusiveness, and non-discrimination to avoid generating biased results and solutions.

As illustrated in other deliverables, the legal framework on Artificial Intelligence is still published in terms of the proposal. Guidelines have been published and are already addressing achieving high trustworthiness while developing algorithms.

At this stage, we deal with two proposals:

- **AI Act Proposal (52)** aims to ensure a well-functioning internal market for artificial intelligence systems where both the benefits and risks of AI are adequately addressed at the Union level. The structure of the Regulation introduces a risk-based approach for the developer to protect fundamental rights by design and by default by introducing technical and organisational measures considered appropriate for the given AI-based system. To this end, the *Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI checklist)* adopted by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence in 2020 is supposed to be applied to drive the ethical-legal compliance of the AI-based solution. It assesses the following different requirements:
 - Human agency and oversight: it is important that no AI system is left completely unsupervised to ensure human control in data pooling, processing, and results analysis.
 - Technical robustness and safety: it is necessary that the technology is compliant with the cybersecurity standards to maintain the data flows always available, confidential, and with the required level of integrity.
 - Privacy and data governance: it is mandatory to respect both data protection and privacy as fundamental rights under the GDPR and national implementations framework.
 - Transparency: data processing procedures shall be transparent and traceable.
 - Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness: it is important that data for algorithms training is selected and processed in a way that the highest variety of information is gathered and processed not to have biased results.
 - Environmental and social well-being: it is necessary to think about durable and sustainable technology starting from the design of the solution.
 - Accountability: being compliant and able to explain and justify each decision taken on ethical legal implications of the R&D&I.

AI Liability Directive Proposal (53) aims to improve the functioning of the internal market by laying down harmonised requirements for non-contractual civil liability for damage caused by the involvement of AI systems. The primary goal of this proposal is to advance the widespread adoption of dependable AI technology, thereby maximizing its advantages within the domestic market. This involves guaranteeing that victims of AI systems receive the same level of protection as those harmed by conventional products.

Furthermore, the proposal seeks to diminish legal ambiguity for companies involved in AI development or usage by addressing potential liability issues and preventing the proliferation of disparate national civil liability regulations tailored specifically to AI.

7.2. Measures to address sensitive data management and disclosure.

The strategies and actions taken to ensure appropriate and secure management of sensitive data in the study and data analysis also concern the processing of special categories of personal data like the health-related ones in the triage operations.

To this end, the data management architecture shall fulfil the principles of minimization, purposes, and accountability by enabling the appropriate first responder to get access and share information for the healthcare protection of the data subject, avoiding that such sensitive data flows could be made accessible and processed by staff not directly involved in the given triage operation.

The legal basis for these data processing activities could be identifiable in Article 9, para II, sub c), h), or i) and not in the data subject consent. The consent might be included as a legal basis for the automated decision-making system aiming at profiling the information related to the patient and predicting direct consequences on the victim. However, in this case, if the developed triage procedure – including automated decision-making systems - is adopted by a law of a Member State, this could be considered a legitimate legal basis to process victims' data directly. As mentioned above, technical, and organisational safeguards shall be put in place to ensure privacy-preserving and data protection to limit the processing to the specific scope and between instructed and authorised staff.

Data could be reported as aggregate and anonymous following the statistics thresholds to avoid possible victim reidentification.

7.3. Action plan in case of ethical and regulatory issues or conflicts

The action plan in place to address any ethical issues or regulatory conflicts that arise during the study or data analysis are the following ones.

Firstly, to rely on the data protection officer and/or an ethical-legal advisor. In the VALKYRIES consortium, for example, a partner – SSSA – acts as an ethical, legal unit, addressing under T1.5 the continuous risk assessment under the data protection and fundamental rights perspectives.

Part of the action plan shall also include the establishment of a detailed governance to make easier the identification of roles and responsibilities in the life cycle of the data analysis.

If necessary, reporting mechanisms from the data subjects and other vulnerable persons and prompt resolution procedures shall be set, including collaboration with relevant regulatory authorities.

Considering the protocols for innovators developed under D1.4 and D1.18 and the common core identified under D3.1 to solve possible conflicts or regulatory issues, accountability, fairness, and transparency shall be applied.

The principle of accountability, emphasized in both the EU data strategy initiatives and those related to AI and cybersecurity, places an obligation on the data controller to justify their actions. This necessitates a prior assessment of risks and potential impacts, followed by ongoing monitoring of the effectiveness of the adopted approach. This principle fosters a responsible mindset and resolves potential conflicts, including allocating roles to substantiate actions taken,

establishing safeguards, and implementing organizational and technical measures for legal compliance.

The principle of transparency extends across technical and legal dimensions. For instance, a transparent development process for a tool entails the clear definition and accessibility of all technical prerequisites. When AI and ML techniques are involved, transparency implies that the models employed should be comprehensible and openly accessible. Additionally, users must be well-informed and aware of data collection, processing, sharing procedures, and more.

The principle of fairness will be helpful in harmonizing conflicting actions by referencing fundamental values enshrined in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. More specifically, fairness is intrinsically linked to the legal concept of good faith, which should guide the development, deployment, and utilization of solutions in various relationships, such as business-to-business, business-to-consumer, and business-to-government contexts. From a technical standpoint, ensuring fairness involves eliminating biases in data processing, thereby enhancing the system's credibility.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable has explored the fundamental principles of datasets, focusing on what datasets are and their types and applications in society. Additionally, we have examined the necessary steps to achieve a clean dataset (identifying and correcting errors and inconsistencies) and to transform the data, for instance, through normalization, discretization, or data generalization. Furthermore, the data need to be balanced to ensure reliable results from the generated machine learning models. Data visualization is of great importance as it helps to identify errors in the data and correct them promptly. Moreover, it can assist in identifying trends that may be difficult to discern through other means. Another aspect covered in this deliverable has been the study of the state of the art regarding datasets used in emergencies. For each dataset studied, an explanation and analysis of the study in which it was conducted have been provided.

The next step involved the creation of a dataset within the Valkyries framework, which was generated using data obtained from the SIGRUN platform during the execution of the first three use cases. The dataset includes clinical details of affected patients, available medical resources, response protocols, outcomes, and other relevant aspects. Once all the data was collected, a data cleaning process was carried out to rename the columns with more descriptive and understandable names, and columns with more than 90% missing values were removed. Additionally, categorical variables were transformed into numerical ones to conduct a correlation analysis of the dataset to identify trends and patterns among the columns, although such patterns were not observed. This transformation is also crucial for creating machine learning models.

The dataset generated after carrying out the above processes could not be compared with the datasets studied in the literature because the dataset generated has extracted and analysed features that are not included in any dataset in the literature, which makes the comparison process impossible as there are no common features.

Another important aspect that has been worked on is the intention to compare the generated dataset with those studied in the literature. However, this process has been impossible because the generated dataset has extracted and analysed features not included in any datasets studied in the literature. This makes the comparison process impossible as they do not have common features.

The final step involved the creation of several machine learning models to predict various outcomes. The first prediction aimed to predict the value of the second triage based on the values obtained during the first triage. Three models were created using different classification algorithms. The Random Forest model achieved a training accuracy of 0.78, a test F1-score of 0.85, and a Kappa index of 0.78. The kNN model achieved a training accuracy of 0.75, a test F1-score of 0.77, and a Kappa index of 0.67. The last algorithm used was Naïve Bayes, which achieved a training accuracy of 0.55, a test F1-score of 0.58, and a Kappa index of 0.41.

The second prediction aimed to predict whether a victim is highly likely to die after the first triage. Three models were generated for this prediction as well. The Random Forest model achieved a training accuracy of 1, a test balanced accuracy of 0.75, a test F1-score of 0.96, and a Kappa index of 0.65. The kNN model achieved a training accuracy of 1, a test balanced accuracy of 0.73, a test F1-score of 0.94, and a Kappa index of 0.47. The Naïve Bayes model achieved a training accuracy of 0.95, a test balanced accuracy of 0.5, a test F1-score of 0.91, and a Kappa index of 0.0.

Based on the information collected during the first triage, the final prediction attempted to predict whether a patient's condition would worsen during the second triage. Using Random Forest as the algorithm, the first model achieved a training accuracy of 0.99, a test balanced accuracy of 0.75, a test F1-score of 0.96, and a Kappa index of 0.65. Using the kNN algorithm, the second model achieved a training accuracy of 0.97, a test balanced accuracy of 0.75, a test F1-score of 0.96, and a Kappa index of 0.65. The last algorithm used was Naïve Bayes, which achieved a training accuracy of 0.65, a test balanced accuracy of 0.75, a test F1-score of 0.96, and a Kappa index of 0.65.

These generated models indicate that it is possible to make a prediction of the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one with high accuracy, as well as to predict in advance whether a victim has a high likelihood of dying after the first triage and to predict whether the condition of an injured person will worsen during the second triage, based on the information from the first triage.

Regarding the compliance with the requirements obtained from task 7.2 of the Valkyries project, based on the results obtained in this deliverable, it can be confirmed that the following requirements have been met:

- REQ_BASE_T7.2_1: Study datasets to create a Valkyries-compatible model.
- REQ_BASE_T7.2_2: Generate rich datasets.
- REQ_BASE_T7.2_3: Obtain information from virtual sensors.
- REQ_BASE_T7.2_4: Inclusion of the minimum data set to the dataset.
- REQ_BASE_T7.2_5: Analyse the dataset and extract more relevant features.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_1: Models integrating data from multiple sources.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_2: Models for optimizing patients care.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_3: Models for recognition of the patients' state.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_5: Datasets to train the models.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_7: Obtain the most relevant features.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_8: Efficient labelling.

However, some requirements have not been able to be fulfilled due to the associated difficulty. These requirements are as follows:

- REQ_BASE_T7.2_6: Comparison of the outcomes with the state-of-the-art.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_4: Reinforcement learning.
- REQ_COM_T7.2_6: Integration with existing software for simulations.

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10. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
BFE	Backward feature elimination
DBSMOTE	Density-Based Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique
DPSS	Discrete Prolate Spheroidal Sequences
EM-DAT	Emergency Events Database
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
FFS	Forward feature selection
GDA	General discriminant analysis
kNN	k-Nearest Neighbors algorithm
KTAS	Korean Triage and Acuity Scale
ML	Machine Learning
OEM	Office of Emergency Management
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique
SSCD	Spatial-spectral combined distance
SSMRPE	Spatial-spectral manifold reconstruction preserving embedding
TFS	Toronto Fire Services

Table 12 - Glossary